

DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13948229>

Spatial distribution of Tsetse fly and prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis in selected sites of Southern Ethiopia

Saifemichael Ushecho Utino ^{1,*}, Wondu Sorsa ²¹ Tocha District Agriculture, Environmental Conservation and Co-operative Office, Ethiopia² Dilla Animal Health Research Centre, Ethiopia

* Corresponding author e-mail: saife.us2007@gmail.com

Received: 29 July 2024; Revised submission: 02 September 2024; Accepted: 03 September 2024

<https://jbrodka.com/index.php/ejbr>Copyright: © The Author(s) 2024. Licensee Joanna Bródka, Poland. This article is an open-access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

ABSTRACT: A cross sectional study was conducted from June 2023 to March 2024 to estimate the prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis and density of Tsetse fly in Southern Ethiopia. Total of 432 blood samples collected from systematically selected cattle and examined using buffy coat and thin blood smear examination. The overall prevalence of trypanosomosis found 6.5% with *Trypanosoma congolense* (78.6%) and *T. vivax* (21.4%) being the causative agents. Significantly higher disease occurrence were observed in lowland areas (7.5%, 95% CI: 5.2-10.7) than highland (1.4%, 95% CI: 0.2-9.4). Similarly, poor body conditioned cattle (13.8%, 95% CI: 9.3-20.0) had shown significantly higher infection than medium (3.2%, 95% CI: 1.2-8.3) and good (0.7%, 95% CI: 0.01-5.1) ($P < 0.05$). The mean PCV value was 25.89 ± 4.57 with significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) was recorded in infected cattle (20.61 ± 3.50) than non-infected (26.25 ± 4.41). Total of 300 flies caught by using 50NGU traps, giving overall apparent density of 0.86 f/t/d for *Glossina pallidipes* and 2.14f/t/d for other biting fly. The study highlights the need for comprehensive control measures, such as use of insecticide-treated targets, traps and chemoprophylaxis, to prevent spread of the disease in the study area.

Keywords: Anca-ocha; *Glossina*; *Trypanosoma congolense*; Trypanosomosis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bovine trypanosomosis is a parasitic infection caused by an extracellular hemoparasites known as trypanosomes. Trypanosomes are unicellular protozoan parasites of phylum Sarcomastigophora, order Kinetoplastida, family Trypanosomatidae and genus *Trypanosoma*, subgenus Nannomonas (*Trypanosoma congolense* species), subgenus Duttonella (*T. vivax* species) and subgenus Trypanozoon (*T. brucei* species) [1]. The most common clinical signs include anaemia, weight loss, reduced productivity, infertility and abortion [2]. It is a serious disease in domestic livestock that causes a significant negative impact in food production and economic growth in many parts of the world [3], particularly in Sub-Saharan Africa [4] and is present in 37 countries in this region. More than one third of the land (~9 million km²) is infested by Tsetse flies [5]. Tsetse and other biting flies have been implicated in the cyclical and mechanical transmission of bovine trypanosomosis and the distribution of the disease corresponds to the distribution of these flies [6].

The disease is more prevalent in the southern part of the Rift Valley, western and Northwestern parts of the country where the primary vectors exist along the great river basin of Abay, Omo, Gibe and Baro. The

most important trypanosome species affecting livestock in Ethiopia are *T. congolense*, *T. vivax* and *T. brucei* in cattle, sheep and goat, *T. evansi* in camel and *T. equiperdum* in horse [7].

According to Langridge [8] and Leta et al. [9], the Tsetse fly vectors in Ethiopia are limited to the western and southern regions between longitude 33° and 38° E and latitude 5° and 12° N infesting areas around 140,000 km² of fertile agricultural land which is roughly 12% of the country's landmass is found a suitable habitat for Tsetse fly. The southern parts of Ethiopia were the most Tsetse fly infested area in the country, due to this reason the country had been started to eradicate Tsetse fly as a project (Southern Tsetse fly eradication project) covering 25,000 km² area 20 years ago and this project brought important change in livestock sectors of the region and now it was changed in to national institute of trypanosomosis and Tsetse fly investigation and eradication with expansion of its coverage in to 79, 000 km² (mainly in Oromia, Southern Ethiopia, Amara, Benshangul Gumize) [10].

Although, several attempts have been made to control trypanosomosis in the area with chemotherapy and chemoprophylaxis as well as vector-targeted control practices that have been implemented mainly through specifically designed joint projects of the Ministry of Agriculture and other non-governmental organization [11] the Tsetse transmitted animal trypanosomosis still remain as one of the major causes of livestock production losses particularly in Ethiopia and specifically in the current study area. Therefore, the objective of this study was to estimate the prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis and its associated risk factors and to determine the apparent density of Tsetse fly as well as to identify the prevailing Tsetse (*Glossina* sp.) species in the study area.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study Area Description

The study was conducted in six purposively selected Districts in southern Ethiopia. A single Keble per Districts was incorporated for this study based on the farmers' complaint about the trypanosomosis and its vectors in the area. The area is characterized by diverse landscapes, ranging from highland areas to lowland plains and experiences a diverse climate due to variations in altitude. The lower-lying areas have a semi-arid to arid climate, while the higher-altitude regions have a cooler and more temperate climate. Livestock rearing is an integral part of the agricultural system in area and Cattle, goats, sheep and poultry are commonly raised. Pastoralism is majorly practiced in the lowland areas, where communities rely on grazing lands for their animals where as in the highland areas, crops such as maize, teff, barley, wheat and beans are grown. The mid-altitude regions are suitable for coffee production, while the lowland areas are used for cultivating drought-tolerant crops like sorghum, millet and sesame (Figure 1) [12].

2.2. Study Design

A cross-sectional study was conducted from June 2023 to March 2024 to estimate the prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis and the apparent density of Tsetse fly and other biting flies in six purposively selected Keble in the Southern Ethiopia.

2.3. Study Population

The study incorporated zebu or local cattle breed of all age groups of both sexes in selected Kebles of the study areas which were managed under extensive husbandry system in communal grazing lands. The age of study animals was estimated by means of their dentition as described by Gatenby [13] and categorized as ≤ 2 years were classified as calves, those above 2-5 years were classified as young, and those ≥ 5 years were adult. The body condition of animals were recorded by classifying animals into three groups as good, medium and

poor based on the appearance of ribs and dorsal spines [14]. The altitude of the study area was categorized as low land and high land based on the elevation of the area.

Figure 1. Study area.

2.4. Sampling Technique and Sample Size Determination

A systematic random sampling technique was applied to select the study animals. The sample size required for the study was calculated by considering the prevalence of 7.2% reported by Sheferaw et al. [15] from southern part of Rift Valley, 95% Confidence Interval (CI) and 5% desired absolute precision. For sample size calculation the following formula described by Thrusfield [16] was used.

$$n = \frac{(1.96^2 * P_{exp} * (1 - P_{exp}))}{d^2}$$

Where n is the required sample size, P_{exp} is the expected prevalence, and d is the desired absolute precision. Accordingly, the calculated sample size required was 101; however, to increase the precision, the sample size was increased by more than 4x; hence, 432 heads of cattle were included in the study area.

2.5. Blood Sampling and Examination

Blood samples were collected into heparinized capillary tubes after piercing the marginal ear vein by using the lancet. One end of the capillary tube was sealed with Cristaseal and centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for five minutes. Then, Packed Cell Volume (PCV) was measured by using hematocrit reader for the determination of the level of anemia. Animals with PCV <25% were designated as anemic [17]. The contents of the capillary tube (including about 1 mm above and below the buffy coat) was expelled by cutting with diamond tipped pen, mixed and spread on a clean glass slide and covered with cover slip. The preparation was then examined under 40x magnifications as a wet preparation and trypanosome species were identified according to their movement as described by OIE [18]. The trypanosome species were identified based on their movement pattern during the buffy coat examination as described by Murray et al. [19]. The confirmation of trypanosome species was done by morphological characteristics after staining the thin blood smear with Giemsa and examination with oil immersion microscopy with ×100 power of magnification [20].

2.6. Entomological Survey

For the entomological study, a total of 50 Niguruman (NGU) traps were deployed in the watering and grazing points of animals at regular interval of 200m for two days. Each trap was supported on a wood pole such that the trap entrance was at a height of about 45cm above the ground. To increase trapping efficiency the chemical known as acetone and Octanol were used [21]. The lower portions of the supporting pole were greased in order to prevent the ants climbing up on the pole towards the collecting cage that could damage the Tsetse flies. The location of each trap was recorded with a Global Positioning System (GPS). After 48 hours of deployment the Tsetse flies in the cages were collected, counted and identified based on the morphological characteristics such as size, color, proboscis and wing venation structures at genus level [22]. Sexing was also done for the flies just by observing the posterior end of the ventral aspect of abdomen by hand lens; as a result, male flies are easily identified by enlarged hypopharynx. Fly catch per trap per day (f/t/d) was determined to calculate the fly density [23].

2.7. Data Analysis

Collected data were entered into Microsoft Excel spread sheet, coded and summarized by descriptive statistics. The prevalence of trypanosomosis calculated as the number of infected cattle divided by the total number of sampled animals and then multiplied by 100. For the statistical analysis STATA software version 14 was used. The association between the risk factors and infection of trypanosome were analyzed with univariable logistic regression. Those risk factors with $p < 0.25$ values were further subjected to multivariable analysis. The mean PCV in parasitemic and aparasitaemic animals was compared using a t-test. The apparent Tsetse density (AD) was expressed as the number of flies per traps per day (F/T/D).

3. RESULTS

3.1. Parasitological findings

Out of the 432 total cattle examined by buffy coat technique, 28 cattle found positive for bovine trypanosomosis, which gives an overall prevalence of 6.5% in the study area. Only *T. congolense* 22 (78.6%) and *T. vivax* 6 (21.4%) was identified in this study. The univariable logistic regression analysis was applied to assess the associations of potential risk factors with the occurrence of bovine trypanosomosis. And the result revealed the occurrence of the disease in the Bilatechericho Keble (12.5%, 95% CI: 6.6-22.4), Abala (9.7%, 95% CI: 4.7-19.0), Gamule (6.9%, 95% CI: 2.9-15.4), Anca ocha (4.2%, 95% CI: 1.3-12.2), Saba (4.2%, 95% CI: 1.4-12.2) and Gemoye (1.4%, 95% CI: 0.2-9.4) without significant difference ($p > 0.05$).

The prevalence of trypanosomosis in male cattle was 6.8% (95% CI: 3.4-11.7) and 6.3% (95% CI: 3.8-10.0) for female without significant difference ($p > 0.05$). The risk of infection of trypanosomes in lowland areas ($< 1500\text{masl}$; 7.5%, 95% CI: 5.2-10.7) was significantly higher than the highland areas ($> 1500\text{masl}$; 1.4%, 95% CI: 0.2-9.4). Moreover, significantly higher proportion of poor body conditioned cattle (13.8%, 95% CI: 9.3-20.0) were infected by trypanosomosis followed by medium (3.2%, 95% CI: 1.2-8.3) and good (0.7%, 95% CI: 0.01-5.1) body conditioned cattle. Though, no significant differences white coat colored cattle were shown the lowest disease infection than the others in this study ($p < 0.05$) (Table 1).

After checking collinearity, those variables with $p < 0.25$ in the univariable logistic regression analysis (Keble, Altitude, BSC and Coat color) were subjected to multivariable logistic regression analysis. Based on the results of the multivariable logistic regression analysis, it was found that only Altitude and BSC were significant risk factors associated with the prevalence of bovine trypanosome infection ($p < 0.05$; Table 2).

Table 1. Univariable logistic regression analysis for bovine trypanosomosis with associated risk factors.

	Variables	No. animals examined	No. infected animals	Prevalence (%), 95%CI	OR	P-value
Keble	Anca ocha	72	3	4.2 (1.3-12.3)	Ref.	-
	Abalamaraka	72	7	9.7 (4.7-19.1)	2.5	0.202
	Bilatechericho	72	9	12.5 (6.6-22.4)	3.3	0.084
	Gamule	72	5	6.9 (2.9-15.7)	1.7	0.471
	Gemoye	72	1	1.4 (0.2-9.4)	0.32	0.334
	Saba	72	3	4.2 (1.3-12.3)	1	1.00
Altitude	Highland	72	1	1.4 (0.2-9.4)	Ref.	-
	Lowland	360	27	7.5 (5.2-10.7)	5.76	0.088
Sex	Female	256	16	6.3 (3.9-10.0)	Ref.	-
	Male	176	12	6.8 (3.9-11.7)	1.09	0.814
Age	Calf	17	1	5.9 (0.8-33.5)	Ref.	-
	Young	105	6	5.7 (2.6-12.2)	1.00	0.978
	Adult	310	21	6.8 (4.4-10.2)	1.20	0.886
BCS	Good	141	1	0.7 (0.01-5.1)	Ref.	-
	Medium	124	4	3.2 (1.2-8.3)	4.67	0.171
	Poor	167	23	13.8 (9.3-20.0)	22.36	0.003
Coat color	Black	31	3	9.7 (3.0-26.5)	Ref.	-
	Mixed	25	3	12.0 (3.8-32.1)	1.27	0.780
	White	137	3	2.2 (0.7-6.6)	0.21	0.063
	Red	239	19	7.9 (5.1-12.1)	0.81	0.741

Table 2. Multivariable logistic regression analysis for potential risk factors.

	Variable	No. animals examined	Prevalence (%), 95%CI	OR	P-value
Altitude	Highland	72	1.4 (0.2-9.4)	Ref.	-
	Lowland	360	7.5 (5.2-10.7)	8.03	0.044
BSC	Good	141	0.7 (0.01-5.1)	Ref.	-
	Medium	124	3.2 (1.2-8.3)	4.91	0.157
	Poor	167	13.8 (9.3-20.0)	25.59	0.002

The Hosmer-Lemeshow goodness-of-fit test was conducted to evaluate how well the multivariable logistic regression model fits the data. The result showed that the model fits the data well ($HL\chi^2 = 1.92$; $p = 0.3832$), indicating that the model is reliable in predicting the risk of trypanosome infection. The Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve was also generated to evaluate the performance of the multivariable logistic regression model. The area under the curve (AUC) was found 0.7876, which suggests that the model has a fair to good discriminatory power in distinguishing between infected and non-infected animals.

3.2. Haematological Findings

The mean PCV value of the animals was $25.89\% \pm 4.57\%$. The mean PCV value was significantly lower ($p < 0.05$) in the *Trypanosoma* infected animals (20.61 ± 3.50) than non-infected animals (26.25 ± 4.41) (Table 3).

Table 3. t-test analysis of mean PCV (%) with associated risk factors.

Variable	Animals observed	Mean PCV (%)	Std. dev.	t-test	P-value	
Infection status	Non-Infected	404	26.25	4.41	6.6338	0.000
	Infected	28	20.61	3.50		
Total	432	25.89	4.57			

3.3. Entomological Findings

A total of 300 flies were caught by using 50 NGU traps in the study area. Among the total flies caught, 86 (28.7%) were *Glossina*, 83 (27.7%) were *Tabanus* and 131 (43.6%) were *Stomoxys*. The *G. pallidipes* was the only *Glossina* species found in the study area during the study period. The study revealed that the overall apparent density of flies was 3.0f/t/d. The apparent density of *G. pallidipes* was 0.86f/t/d and that of biting flies was 2.14f/t/d (*Tabanus* 0.83f/t/d and *Stomoxys* 1.31f/t/d) (Table 4).

Table 4. The distribution and apparent density of flies in the study area.

Keble	Altitude (masl)	No trap deployed	<i>Glossina pallidipes</i>					Bitingflies		Overall	
			M	F	Total	f/t/d	T	S	Total	f/t/d	
Abalam araka	1266	10 NGU	5	17	22	1.1	15	31	46	2.3	3.4
Anca ocha	1409	10NGU	4	10	14	0.7	10	11	21	1.05	1.75
Bilatech ericho	1334	10NGU	5	17	22	1.1	17	31	48	2.4	3.5
Gemoye	968	10NGU	4	11	15	0.75	15	28	43	2.15	2.9
Saba	874	10NGU	3	10	13	0.65	26	30	56	2.8	3.45
Total		50	21	65	86	0.86	83	131	214	2.14	3.0

NB. M=Male, F=Female, T=Tabanus, S=Stomoxys, f/t/d=fly/trap/day

4. DISCUSSION

The study investigated the prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis and the density and distribution of Tsetse fly and other biting flies in selected sites of Southern Ethiopia. The overall prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis in the area was 6.5%, which is comparable with the prevalence reported from Kindo Koisha District of Wolaita Zone (6.3%) [24], Bako Tibe, West Shoa and Gobu Seyo West Wollega Zone (6.25%) [25] and Chilga District of Northwest Ethiopia (6.2%) [26]. This correspondence may be due to similarity of agro-ecological conditions and management systems practiced in these areas.

In contrast, higher prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis reported a prevalence of 14.8% from Dara District, Sidama Zone, Southern Ethiopia [27], 11.16% from Sadi Chanka District, Western Oromia [28] and 11.46% from Benatsemay District, Southern Ethiopia [29]. Similarly, higher prevalence of trypanosomosis has been reported from Suba and Teso in Kenya by Thumbi et al. [30] and East Zambia by Mulenga et al. [31].

The lower prevalence in the current study areas relative to the other areas might be due to low density of vectors, treatment of infected animals by using trypanocidal drugs by animal owners as well as the animal health experts and progressive control measures such as chemical application on the back of the animals, the use of insecticide-impregnated targets as well as traps under taken by the Arbaminch Animal Health Research Center (AAHRC) and Arbaminch Animal Health Research Center Dilla branch. However, in other papers [32-35] have been reported the lower prevalence of the disease from different parts of Ethiopia and Eastern Africa. The variation in prevalence of the trypanosomosis might be due to differences in the study area, investigator experience and the time of the study.

T. congolense was the dominant *Trypanosoma* species followed by *T. vivax* was identified in the study area. This is in agreement with reports from Loka Abaya [36], Loma district, southern Ethiopia [37], Benatsemay District, Southern Ethiopia [29] and Rift Valley of Gamo Zone [38]. The predominance of *T. congolense* infection in cattle of Tsetse-infested areas may be due to the high tendency of the parasite to develop new strains capable of escaping the host immune response. The host has the potential to the development of better immune response against *T. vivax* compared to *T. congolense* infections [39].

Among the potential risk factors considered during the study; Altitude difference and BSC of the animal were significantly influencing the prevalence of trypanosomosis ($p < 0.05$). The prevalence of trypanosomosis was significantly higher in Lowland areas than in Highland areas and this finding was in line with report from Kellem Wollega, Western Ethiopia [40] and Sayo District, Oromia Regional State, Western Ethiopia [41]. This might be attributed to higher challenge of vectors in lowland areas. Hence, altitude affects the distribution and abundance of the Tsetse fly, which is the primary vector for transmitting trypanosomes to cattle. Tsetse flies are generally more prevalent in lower altitude regions, particularly in areas with suitable vegetation cover and suitable climatic conditions [23].

The significant association between body condition score of cattle and trypanosome infection was observed in this study ($p > 0.05$). Poor body conditioned animals were highly affected by the trypanosomosis, which is followed by medium and good body conditioned animals. This finding was in agreement with the studies [36, 37, 41], who found the highest prevalence of trypanosomosis in animals with poor body condition. This might be attributed by reduced resistance of those animals having poor body condition or related to the progressive weight loss arising from debilitating nature of the disease itself. In other hand, not all animals with poor body condition were found positive for trypanosomosis in this study. This could be due to malnutrition, internal parasites and other body loss causing diseases [42].

The overall mean PCV value of all studied cattle was $25.89\% \pm 4.57\%$. In this study, the mean PCV of trypanosome infected cattle was significantly lower ($t=6.6338$; $P < 0.05$) than non-infected cattles. The lowered mean PCV of trypanosome infected animals was also reported from various parts of Ethiopia [40, 41, 43, 44] and Zambia [45]. One of the common symptoms of animal trypanosomosis is anemia, which is characterized by a decrease in the number of red blood cells [45-47]. However, not all infected animals developed anemia in this study. This may possibly explained the severity of the anemia can vary depending on several factors, including the species and breed of the animals, the strain and virulence of the parasite, the duration and intensity of the infection, and the nutritional status of the animal [48].

The entomological survey conducted in this study revealed the presence of only one *Glossina* species known as *G. pallidipes* as well as other biting flies such as *Stomoxys* and *Tabanus*. The overall apparent density of *G. pallidipes* was 0.86f/t/d and 2.14f/t/d for biting flies (*Tabanus* 0.83f/t/d and *Stomoxys* 1.31f/t/d). Related findings were reported from Gambela and Abobo districts (0.75f/t/d) [49] and Mareka District of Dawuro Zone, Southern Ethiopia (0.48 f/t/d) by [50]. However, the higher overall apparent density of *Glossina* were reported from Didesa District of Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia (4.91 f/t/d) [43], Gidami district (3.06f/t/d) and Sayo district (4.16f/t/d) [51], 11.6 flies/trap/day Botor Tolay District, Jimma Zone, Ethiopia [52] and Rift Valley of Gamo Zone, Southern Ethiopia (12.85f/t/d) [38]. In general, the differences in apparent densities and distributions of *Glossina* in the current study area and other parts of Ethiopia as well as Africa could be differences in habitat, climatic condition, host availability, control measures undertaken and human activities [53].

5. CONCLUSIONS

The current study revealed the occurrence of bovine trypanosomosis and its vectors in the area. The overall prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis in the area was found 6.5%, with a significantly higher infection in the lowland areas (7.5%) compared to the highlands (1.4%). Similarly, statistically significant proportion of Poor body conditioned cattles (13.8%) infected by trypanosomosis than the medium (3.2%) and the good (0.7%) body conditioned cattle. *T. congolense* and *T. vivax* were the two predominant *Trypanosoma* species which are responsible for bovine trypanosomosis in the study area. During the entomological study, a total of 300 flies (86 *Glossina* and 214 other biting flies) were caught by using 50NGU traps which gives the overall density of 0.86f/t/d for *Glossina* and 2.14f/t/d for other biting flies.

Based on the conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendation was forwarded:

- Use targets and traps treated with insecticides in areas where Tsetse flies are abundant.
- Apply insecticides to cattle, such as pour-on formulations or insecticide-impregnated ear tags, it may repel or kill Tsetse flies.
- Treat cattle with trypanocidal drugs on a regular basis which can prevent the establishment of parasite infections.
- Educating farmers and livestock keepers about the transmission, economic impacts and prevention of bovine trypanosomosis should not be neglected.

Author Contributions: SU involved in study design, performed data analysis, and wrote the final manuscript. WS involved in study design, field data collection and laboratory examinations. Both authors read and approved the final version of the manuscript. Both authors contributed equally.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no potential conflict of interest.

Source of Funding: This work has not received any financial support.

Ethics approval: The animal study was reviewed and approved by Animal Research Ethics Review Committee of Arbaminch Animal Health Research Center. Written informed consent was obtained from the owners for the participation of their animals in this study.

REFERENCES

1. Eloy LJ, Lucheis SB. Canine Trypanosomosis, etiology of infection and implications for public health. *Anim Toxins Incl Trop Dis*. 2009; 15: E589-E611.
2. Taylor K, Authié E. Pathogenesis of African Trypanosomosis. In: I Maudlin PH Holmes MA Miles. *The Trypanosomosis*. Wallingford: CAB International, 2004: 331-353.
3. Taylor A, Co P, Wall L. *Veterinary Parasitology*, 3rd ed. UK. Blackwell publishing, 2007: 44-102.
4. Cecchi G, Mattioli R, Slingenbergh J, De La Rocque S. Land cover and tsetse fly distributions in sub-Saharan Africa. *Med Vet Entomol*. 2008; 22(4): E364–E373.
5. Rogers D, Robinson T. Tsetse distribution. In: Maudlin, I, et al. (Eds.) *The trypanosomosis*. Wallingford, UK: CABI International, 2004: 139-179.
6. OIE (World Animal Health Organization). *Trypanosomosis, Tsetse-Transmitted*. OIE Terrestrial Manual. OIE, Rome, Italy, 2013; <http://www.oie.int>.
7. Abebe G. Trypanosomosis in Ethiopia. *Ethiopia J Biol Sci*. 2005; 4: E75-E121.
8. Langridge W. *Tsetse and Trypanosomosis Survey of Ethiopia*. Ministry of Overseas Department UK Scientific Research Publishing, 1976.

9. Leta S, Alemayehu G, Seyoum Z, Bezie M. Prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis in Ethiopia: a meta-analysis. *Parasites Vectors*. 2016; 9(1): E1–E9.
10. Alembo E. Prevalence of Bovine Trypanosomosis and Tsetse Fly Density in Different Regions of Ethiopia. A Review. *J Vet Sci Technol*. 2019; 10: E583.
11. Tafese W, Melaku A, Fentahun T. Prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis and its vectors in two districts of East Wollega zone, Ethiopia. *Onderstepoort J Vet Res*. 2012; 79: E123-E128.
12. DAHRC. Dilla Animal Health Research Center Annual report. Dilla. 2024.
13. Gatensby R. *The Tropical Agriculture*. London and Bering Stock Mc Millan Education Ltd, London, 1991.
14. Nicholson M, Butterworth M. *A Guide to Condition Scoring of Zebu Cattle*. International Livestock center for Africa, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 1986: E1-E29.
15. Sheferaw D, Birhanu B, Asrade B, Abera, M, Tusse T. Bovine trypanosomosis and glossina distribution in selected areas of southern part of Rift Valley, Ethiopia. *Acta Trop*. 2015; 154: E145-E148,.
16. Thrusfield M. *Veterinary epidemiology 4th edition*. Veterinary Clinical Studies Royal (Dick) School of Veterinary Studies. University of Edinburgh, 2018: E275-E276.
17. Douglas J, Wardrop K. *Schalm's Veterinary Hematology*, 6th edn. Blackwell, Oxford, 2010.
18. OIE (World Animal Health Organization). *Trypanosomosis: Manual of Diagnostic Tests and Vaccines for Terrestrial Animals*. France, 2013, www.oie.int.
19. Murray M, Murray PK, McIntyre WI. An improved technique for the diagnosis of African trypanosomosis. *Trans R. Soc Trop Med Hyg*. 1977; 71: E325-E326.
20. Luckins A. Methods for diagnosis of trypanosomosis in livestock. *World Animal Rev*. 1992; 70: 15-20.
21. Malele I, Craske L, Knight C, Ferris VV, Njiru Z, Hamilton P, et al. The use of specific and generic primers to identify trypanosome infections of wild tsetse in Tanzania by PCR. *Infect Gen Evol*, 2003; 3: E271-E279.
22. Gibson W, Bailey M. The development of Trypanosome brucei within the tsetse fly midgut observed using green fluorescent trypanosomes. *Kinetoplastid Biol Dis*. 2003; 2(1): 1.
23. Pollock J. *Training Manual for Tsetse Control Personnel*. Tsetse Biology, Systematics and Distribution, Techniques. FAO, I. Rome, 1982.
24. Adale E, Yasine A. Prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis in Wolaita Zone Kindo Koisha District of Ethiopia. *Afr J Agricult Res*. 2013; 8: E6383-E6387.
25. Abera Z, Fekadu M, Kabeta T, Kebede G, Mersha T. Prevalence of Bovine Trypanosomosis in Bako Tibe District of West Shoa and Gobu Seyo Districts of West Wollega Zone, Ethiopia. *Eur J Biol Sci*. 2014; 6: E71-E80.
26. Seyoum Z, Abera D. Prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis in Chilga District, Northwest Ethiopia; Using Aldehyde and Parasitological testse. *Acad J Microbiol Res*. 2016; 4: E072-E077.
27. Keffale M, Shabula Z, Tamerat N. Prevalence of bovine trypanosomiasis in Dara District Sidama Zone, Southern Ethiopia. *J Parasitol Vector Biol*. 2017; 9: E132-E136.
28. Emiru W, Dinbasha E, Dagafa W, Kune A. Prevalence of Bovine Trypanosomosis in and Around Sadi Chanka District, Western Oromia. *Bio Med J Sci Tech Res*. 2022; 42(5): 33947-33952.
29. Fesseha H, Eshetu E, Mathewos M, Tilante T. Study on Bovine Trypanosomosis and Associated Risk Factors in Benatsemay District, Southern Ethiopia. *Environ Health Insights*. 2022; 16: E1-E10.
30. Thumbi S, Jung'a J, Mosi R, McOdimba F. Spatial distribution of African Animal Trypanosomiasis in Suba and Teso districts in Western Kenya. *BMC Res*. 2010; 3: 6.
31. Mulenga G, Namangala B, Gummow B. Prevalence of trypanosomes and selected symbionts in tsetse species of eastern Zambia. *Parasitology*. 2022; 149: E1406–E1410.

32. Biyazen H, Duguma R, Asaye M. Trypanosomosis, Its Risk Factors, and Anaemia in Cattle Population of Dale Wabera District of Kellem Wollega Zone, Western Ethiopia. *J Vet Med*. 2014; 374191: 6.
33. Girma K, Meseret T, Tilahun Z, Haimanot D, Firew L, Tadele K, Zelalem A. Revalence of Bovine Trypanosomosis, its Vector Density and Distribution in and Around Arbaminch, Gamogofa Zone, Ethiopia. *Acta Parasitol Glob*. 2014; 5(3): E169-E176.
34. Kivali V, Kiyong'a A, Fyfe J, Toye P, Fèvre E, Cook E. Spatial Distribution of Trypanosomes in Cattle from Western Kenya. *Front Vet Sci*. 2027; 7: 554.
2. Katabazi A, Almustapha A, GiftWitto S, Odoki M, Musinguz S. Prevalence of *Trypanosoma congolense* and *Trypanosoma vivax* in Lira District, Uganda. *Biomed Res Int*. 2021: 1-7.
35. Abebe L, Dessie M, Solomon M. Bovine Trypanosomosis and Tsetse Fly Densities during the wet humid period in Loka Abaya District of Sidama National Regional State, Southern Ethiopia. *J Entomol Nematol*. 2021; 13: E12-E18.
3. Eyasu T, Mekuria S, Sheferaw D. Seasonal prevalence of trypanosomosis, *Glossina* density and infection along the escarpment of Omo River, Loma district, Southern Ethiopia. *Heliyon*, 20217; e06667.
36. Seyoum W, Tora E, Kore K, Lejebo F. Seasonal Patterns: Bovine Trypanosomosis, *Glossina pallidipes* Density and Infection in Rift Valleys of Gamo Zone, Southern Ethiopia. *Front Vet Sci*. 2022; 9: 805564.
37. Leak SG. *Tsetse Biology and Ecology: their role in the epidemiology and control Trypanosomosis*. CABI Publishing in association with the ILRI, 1999: E152-E210.
38. Tsegaye D, Terefe G, Delema D, Tadesse A. Bovine trypanosomosis and its vectors: prevalence and control operations in Kellem Wollega, Western Ethiopia. *Vet J*. 2020; 25: E60-E84.
39. Efreem D, Kassa T, Kebede N, Worku T. Seasonal prevalence of bovine trypanosomosis and trypanosome species distribution in Jimma Horo district, Oromia regional state, Western Ethiopia. *Parasite Epidemiol Control*. 2023; 20: E00280.
40. Constable P, Hinchcliff K, Done S, Grünberg W. *Veterinary Medicine: A Textbook of the Diseases of Cattle, Horses, Sheep, Pigs, and Goats*. 11th ed. St. Louis, MO: Elsevier Ltd. 2017: E2150-E2156.
41. Fayisa G, Mandefro A, Hailu B, Chala G, Alemayehu G. Epidemiological Status and Vector Identification of Bovine Trypanosomosis in Dideda District of Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia. *Int J Nutr Food Sci*. 2015; 4: 373-380.
42. Abdeta D. Bovine Trypanosomosis Epidemiology and Tsetse Fly Density in Jimma Arjo District, East Wollega Zone, Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia. *Vet Med Res Rep*. 2021; 12: E285-E292.
43. Marcotty T, Simukoko H, Berkvens D, Vercruyse J, Praet N, Van den Bossche P. Evaluating the use of packed cell volume as an indicator of trypanosomal infections in cattle in Eastern Zambia. *Prev Vet Med*. 2008; 87: E288-E300.
44. Desquesnes M, Holzmüller P, Lai D, Dargantes A, Lun Z, Jittapalapong S. *Trypanosoma evansi* and *surra*: a review and perspectives on transmission, epidemiology and control, impact, and zoonotic aspects. *BioMed Res Int*. 2013: E22.
45. Gonzatti M, González-Baradat B, Aso P, Reyna-Bello A. *Trypanosoma (Duttonella) vivax* and Trypanosomosis in Latin America: secadera/huequera/cachohueco. In: Magez S, Radwanska M. (Eds.), *Trypanosomes and Trypanosomosis*. Springer, 2014: E261-E285.
46. Morrison L, Vezza L, Rowan T, Hope J, Entrican G. The bovine trypanosome-specific antibody response to *Trypanosoma congolense* and *Trypanosoma vivax* infections in cattle. *Annu Trop Med Parasitol*. 2008; 102(2): E161-E171.
47. Kedir M, Lelisa K, Damena D. Bovine Trypanosomosis and Tsetse Fly Vectors in Abobo and Gambela Districts, Southwestern Ethiopia. *J Vet Sci Technol*. 2016; 7: E380.
48. Eshetu E, Barata B. The Distribution of Tsetse Flies Species and other Biting Flies in Mareka District of Dawuro Zone, Southern Ethiopia. *Int J Adv Res Biol Sci*. 2017; 4(10): E10-E14.

49. Degneh E. Bovine Trypanosomosis: Epidemiology and Drug Resistance study in selected sites of KellemWollega Zone, Oromia Regional State, Ethiopia. PhD Dissertation, Bishoftu, Ethiopia, Addis Ababa University, 2019.
50. Megersa L, Feyisa B, Dereje A, Behabtom M. Prevalence of Bovine Trypanosomosis and Apparent Density of Tsetse Fly in Botor Tolay District, Jimma Zone, Ethiopia. *Biomed J Sci Tech Res.* 2019; 13(3): 002401.
51. Leak S, Mulatu W, Rowlands G. Risk factors related to the presence of tsetse flies in the Southern Rift Valley of Ethiopia. *Ann Trop Med Parasitol.* 1999; 93: E627-E635.
52. Simarro P, Cecchi G, Franco J, Paone M, Diarra A, Ruiz-Postigo J, Fèvre E. Estimating and mapping the population at risk of sleeping sickness. *PLoS Neglect Trop Dis.* 2010; 4(1): E659.
53. Mihret E, Abebe B, Abebe Y. Assessment of tsetse fly abundance and its associated risk factors in and around Arba Minch, Southern Ethiopia. *J Vet Med Animal Health.* 2015; 7(3): 63-72.